

THE BENEFITS OF USING INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGY IN EDUCATION

¹Ro'zmetova Mohinur Anvarbek qizi, ²Matenova Feruza Maxamatali qizi

¹Chirchiq Davlat pedagogika universiteti, Boshlang'ich ta'lim fakulteti, Maktabgacha va boshlang'ich talimda xorijiy til yo'nalishi 1-bosqich talabasi

²Ilmiy rahbar, Chirchiq davlat pedagogika universiteti, Boshlang'ich ta'lim nazariyasi o'qituvchisi

¹ruzmatovamohinur@gmail.com, ² nimadir.fmm@gmail.com

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10802472>

Abstract. *Technology is an essential part of the world of w which we live. Most of the jobs that did not require technology use in years past do require the use of technology today. Many more homes have computers than in years past and increasing numbers of people know how to use them. Technology is being used by children and adults on a daily basis by way of web surfing, texting, social networking, interactive games, and in more ways. We are an evolving technological society and in many ways have become dependent on its use. Thus, the use of technology and teaching students have to use it has become a high priority in the public schools.*

Keywords: *education, teaching methods, technology, creative, collaborative, integration, development, advancement, essential skills, next generation.*

Ключевые слова: *образование, методы обучения, технологии, творчество, сотрудничество, интеграция, развитие, продвижение, необходимые навыки, следующее поколение.*

Kalit so'zlar: *ta'lim, o'qitish usullari, texnologiya, ijodiy, hamkorlik, integratsiya, rivojlanish, rivojlanish, muhim ko'nikmalar, keyingi avlod.*

Main part.

Interactive techniques have a positive impact on student learning. Technology causes students to be more engaged; thus, students often retain more information. Because of the arrival of new technologies rapidly occurring globally, technology is relevant to the students. Technology provides meaningful learning experiences. Technology also provides hands-on learning opportunities that can be integrated into all school curricular areas, including mathematics, reading, science, and social studies as well as other academic subjects. It gives students opportunities to collaborate with their peers resulting in learning from each other. These factors combined can lead to a positive impact on student learning and motivation.

Students today live in a very technological world. Most students use some form of technology on a daily basis including; texting, social networking, and web surfing. Students see these types of technologies as useful and extremely enjoyable. These very same students that are accustomed to these types of technologies will relate to using technology at school. If their learning environment mirrors the ways in which they engage with the world, they will excel in their education. Technology can transform the classroom into an interactive learning environment. Technology is a powerful contributor to learning if it is used to deepen students' engagement in meaningful and intellectually authentic curriculum.

Technology is a hint. It should be selected when it is the best tool for students to learn. Technology can be a particularly effective tool for English language learners and can enhance the participation of children with disabilities. Children in elementary schools should begin to use familiar technology tools as a part of their academic program. Teachers should model the use of technology in support of the curriculum so that children can see the appropriate use of technology

and benefit from exposure to more advanced applications that they will use independently when they are older.

One study was conducted to examine the experiences of pre-service teachers implementing technology in math lessons. The study shows a positive effect on student learning in mathematics. The pre-service teachers noted that the internet provided math activities at different levels, which gave students an opportunity to choose the level they are comfortable working. Findings showed that students were engaged during the math lessons using technology and students were able to discuss what they learned the following day. The teachers were surprised by the students' recall of the lesson. Some students who participated in the lessons believed that the computer helped them understand what the teacher was saying about the lesson. Technology can be used as a way to create a hands-on and meaningful math lesson.

Continuing advancements in technology change the ways all people live and work. The internet is becoming a common learning tool in many classrooms. This means providing a meaningful learning experience for all students. Teachers today have many opportunities to use technology increasing the ways students learn. Using computers and the internet has become an integral part of our daily lives. Therefore, one of the greatest vehicles for the 21st century is using technology for effective and permanent learning. The internet affects peoples' lives by increasing communication, expanding educational services, and increasing quality along with personal interaction. More emphasis has been placed on seeking, evaluating, organizing using and sharing information with others. The internet is the greatest source for information and the best way to quickly share and exchange information with others. The internet sharpens one's ability to search and analyze information.

Technology is capable of unlocking keys of learning with all students. This includes students with special learning needs. The Etiwanda School District in California has implemented a technology integration program district wide. Teachers received technology training and then began integrating technology into general education lessons on a daily basis. This program also included a practical technology support plan for teachers working with students with special needs. This plan enabled teachers to help these students by weaving technology resources into instruction in meaningful ways.

Conclusion.

The evidence in this paper shows that technology has a positive effect on student learning expectations and outcomes. Evidence also shows that technology integration is becoming more common in public and private schools. Technology integration is shown to be effective in all age groups and is also shown to be helpful for students with special learning needs. To reiterate, technology integration has the following benefits: 1) increased student motivation; 2) increased student engagement; 3) increased student collaboration; 4, increased hands-on learning opportunities; 5) allows for learning at all levels; 6) increased confidence in students, and 6) increased technology skills.

REFERENCES

1. Alexander L. G. A First Book in Comprehension Precis and Composition.— London, 1969.
2. Barker L. L. Listening Behavior.— N.J., 1971.
3. Belanoff P., Dickson M. Portfolios: Process and product.— Portsmouth, VI: Boynton/Cook, 1991.— 270 p.

4. Gottlieb M. Nurturing student learning through portfolios//TESOL Journal.— 1995.—Vol. 5/1.— P. 12-14.
5. Kilpatrick W. H. Foundations of Method: Informal Talks an Teaching. 1918.— No 7.
6. The Cambridge Guide to Teach English to Speakers of other languages / Ed. by R. Carter, D. Nunan//CUP, 2001. — 294 p.
7. Matenova F.M. Words as the main unit of language and speech// 2023-12/4 Вестник Хорезмской академии Маъмуна.— 94 стр.
8. UnderhillA. Process in Humanistic educhtion//ELT Journal 1989. — Vol. 43/4.
9. Wauters J. K. Evaluation for empowerment//Portfolios: Process and product/Ed. by P. Belanoff, M. Dickson. Portsmouth, NH: Heinemann, 1991.— P. 57-68.
10. Wishon G., Barks J. Let's Write English.— No 7.— 1968.